
Classroom Design's Cognitive Impact

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SUMMARY

Existing Knowledge:

1. Classroom design, including lighting, color, and geometry, influences cognitive functions like attention and memory.
2. Lighting (illuminance and color temperature) has been linked to better academic performance and concentration.
3. Virtual Reality (VR) enables precise analysis of design variables' effects on cognition.

New Insights:

1. Lighting is the most significant design element, enhancing males' memory, females' attention, and overall classroom preference.
2. Color influences females' attention significantly, with variations in saturation and hue playing key roles.
3. Geometry (ceiling height and width) has the least cognitive impact but still

affects attention under specific conditions.

Putting Research into Practice:

1. Prioritize lighting adjustments in classrooms to enhance cognitive outcomes without major structural changes.
2. Use color strategically to improve attention, particularly among female students.
3. Consider gender-specific preferences and responses when designing or modifying educational spaces.

Keywords: classroom design, cognitive processes, lighting, color, geometry, Virtual Reality

Reference:

Nolé Fajardo, M. L., Higuera-Trujillo, J. L., & Llinares, C. (2023). Lighting, colour and geometry: Which has the greatest influence on students' cognitive processes? *Frontiers of Architectural Research*, 12(575–586).
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